

Interaction Between Certain Cations and the Humic Acid Extracted from Different Gujarat Soils

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Humus is a colloidal complex body, the exact nature of which depends on its origin and its mode of formation. The entire fraction of soil humus behaves as colloidal complexes and possesses exchange properties.

The complexes of metal-humic acid were studied potentiometrically in presence of various metal ions like Fe^{+3} , Al^{+3} , Cu^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Zn^{+2} , Co^{+3} , Mn^{+2} and K^+ .

The study of properties of humic acid complexes of metal ions can be used in plant nutrition and plant growth study.

SOIL organic matter has long been known to be capable of complexing metals. These complexes influence the availability of the metals to plants¹⁻⁴. Soil organic matter can form stable complexes with metal ions but much remains to be learnt of the mechanisms involved in these reactions. These reactions depend upon the kind and number of functional groups present on the exchange sites⁵. The complex formation of cations with humic acid fraction of soil organic matter is slowly becoming more and more important; since they play a significant role in plant nutrition. It is believed that ion exchange, surface adsorption, chelation and peptization processes are involved in these reactions⁶⁻¹¹.

In this paper, an attempt has been made to study the interaction of certain metallic ions and the extracted humic acids of four different soils of Gujarat. Potentiometric titrations in presence of cations were carried out; the titration curves showed the formation of metal-humic acid complexes. Soils selected for the study have different proportions of organic matter; ranging from 1 to 3% (Ahwa-2.91, Junagadh-1.78, Piplod-2.0, Rajkot-1.02). Number of dissociation constants of extracted humic acids of these soils have been found to be two.

Experimental

Humic acids were extracted from different soils of Gujarat (Ahwa, Junagadh, Piplod, Rajkot) by alkali method and were purified by HCl+HF treatment, dialysis and using ion exchange column-(Amberlite-IR-120)¹²⁻¹⁴. 0.010 gm of extracted humic acid was taken in 100 ml of double distilled water and 2 ml of 0.02 M metal ion solution was added and pH titration was carried out using 0.01 N NaOH solution. No attempt was made to keep the ionic strength constant. Beckman pH meter was used and was standardized with

buffers of pH 4.0 and pH 7.0. A.R. grade chemicals were used for preparation of metal chloride solutions. All solutions used in the above study were prepared in double distilled water. The titrations reading are depicted graphically in Figs 1-3. Tables 1 and 2 present calculation of release of protons (H^+) at pH 7.5 and 8.0.

Fig. 1

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Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

Discussion

Titration curves of the extracted humic acids with metal ions are shown in Figs. 1-3. The formation of metal hydroxides was indicated by the inflections in the

titration curves. The basicity of the extracted humic acids can be obtained from the shape of the titration curves. When 2 ml of 0.02 M salt solution was titrated, metal-complex formation as well as the precipitation of metal hydroxides occurred in stages.

When the titrant 0.01N NaOH solution is added, the following reactions may take place in absence of metal ions as well as in presence of metal ions.

From the titration curves of humic acids in presence of metal ions it is found that the curves for Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II) are very close to each other and there is slight displacement of the titration curves upon the addition of these metals. But in the case of Zn(II), Cu(II), Fe(III), and Al(III), the displacement is high. It is also found that the curve of Zn intersects the curve of Cu(II) at pH near about 7.2 to 7.5. This is perhaps, due to the formation of Zn(ONa)₂ after pH 7.5¹⁵⁻¹⁶.

Beckwith⁷ pointed out that the ability of the metal ions to form complexes with humus substances depends upon the relative pH drop on the addition of the respective metal ions to humus substances. Humus substances have the ability to form complexes or chelates with the metal ions because of the presence in their molecules of hydrophilic groups situated inside radicals.

It has been shown that the interactions of metal ions with humic acid causes the displacement of H from some of the functional groups and the formation of complex compounds^{6,9,10,17,18}. Release of proton

TABLE 1—CALCULATION OF RELEASE OF PROTONS (H⁺) AT pH 7.5

Metal ion	Blank	Ahwa	Junagadh	Piplod	Rajkot
Fe ⁺⁺	3.40	2.85	2.83	2.85	2.75
Al ⁺⁺	2.75	2.30	2.25	2.40	2.23
Cu ⁺⁺	2.15	1.23	1.35	1.23	1.68
Zn ⁺⁺	2.38	1.43	1.35	1.70	1.70
Ni ⁺⁺	0.55	0.10	0.15	0.15	0.70
Co ⁺⁺	0.60	0.38	0.25	0.13	0.65
Mn ⁺⁺	0.35	0.30	0.28	0.10	0.38

TABLE 2—CALCULATION OF RELEASE OF PROTONS (H⁺) AT pH 8.0

Metal ion	Blank	Ahwa	Junagadh	Piplod	Rajkot
Fe ⁺⁺	3.50	2.63	2.70	2.75	2.50
Al ⁺⁺	3.00	2.20	2.15	2.50	2.50
Cu ⁺⁺	2.23	0.90	0.95	0.95	1.93
Zn ⁺⁺	2.68	1.33	1.25	1.63	1.75
Ni ⁺⁺	1.08	0.08	0.13	0.80	1.00
Co ⁺⁺	1.73	0.58	0.50	0.50	1.00
Mn ⁺⁺	1.73	0.58	0.25	0.75	0.20

from various metal humic acid complexes were calculated at different pH values; viz. 7.5 and 8.0 according to Martell and Calvin¹⁹. Results are given in tables 1 and 2. Theoretically, complete complex formation of divalent cation with humic acids should release 2 protons per mole of the metal ion or cation. On the other hand, the release of protons equivalent to the number released by metal alone would indicate that the complex formation with extracted humic acids did not occur but that basic salts were formed. The number of protons set free per mole of added metal were calculated at pH values of 7.5 and 8.0 from the titration curves (Figs. 1-3). For the calculations, the following equations were employed.

- (I) (i) 1000 ml 1N NaOH \equiv 1 gm equivalent of H
 (ii) X ml of 0.01N NaOH \equiv 0.001 x X x 0.01
 (II) 2 ml of 0.02 M metal added (0.02 M mole)
 $\frac{0.02 \times 2}{1000}$
 (III) Number of proton (H⁺)

$$= \frac{0.001 \times X \times 0.01}{0.04/1000} = X/4$$

X = difference of 0.01 N NaOH at the particular pH, between (a) metal ion + humic acid, and (b) humic acid alone.

The additional consumption of alkali in the presence of metallic cations was caused by neutralization of protons released from the functional groups of the extracted humic acids. Over the pH range of titrations, the proton release of all the cations (Fe⁺³, Al⁺³, Cu⁺², Zn⁺², Ni⁺², Co⁺², Mn⁺²)-humic acid complexes never equalled to that of the metal alone (Diags. 1-3). For example, in the presence of one mole of Zn⁺², the proton released at pH 8.0 (Table-2) from soils; Ahwa, Junagadh, Piplod, Rajkot were 1.33, 1.25, 1.63, 1.75 respectively. The corresponding values for Zn⁺² alone was found to be 2.68. These observations further suggested that the added cations formed complexes with the extracted acids. Over the pH range used in the experiments (pH 7.5 and pH 8.0), the number of protons release did not approach the blank values. Similar remarks may be applied to trivalent cations (Fe⁺³, Al⁺³). From the table, it is clear that proton values in the presence of these cations are definitely lower as compared to blank values. However, it may be mentioned that above pH 8.0, hydroxocomplexes of the cations may also be formed. Again in the case of extracted humic acid from Rajkot soil, the discrepancies may be ascribed to the nature of climatic zones (Ahwa, Junagadh and Piplod are classified as forest soils while Rajkot is a semiarid soil).

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